

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI MILANO

10 PRINCIPLES

AI

Governing ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE within the University

The University of Milan intends to foster the use of Artificial Intelligence tools to support all its activities, while holding firm that individuals are at the core of each of its initiatives. Therefore, the goal of the document "Governing Artificial Intelligence within the University" is not to provide limits, but rather to promote an ethical, legally-compliant and conscious use of Artificial Intelligence tools, by implementing the latest regulatory provisions on the subject, as well as best practices already adopted by many universities and research centres in Italy and abroad.

The ten general principles stated in this document will be accompanied by specific guidelines on the use of AI for research, public engagement, knowledge transfer, teaching and administrative activities, including a list of the AI tools cleared for use by the University. These guidelines will be drafted following a participatory process involving representatives from all groups within the academic community.

GENERAL PRINCIPLES

Ten principles for an ethical, legally-compliant and conscious use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in all activities of the University of Milan

1

AI Literacy

The University promotes training courses as well as cultural, technical, legal, scientific and educational events — both in-person and online — to improve AI literacy levels and AI-related digital skills within the University of Milan.

This is done to increase everyone's knowledge, adhere to legal obligations and best practices, and enhance critical thinking within the academic community (technical, administrative and library

staff, students, professors, researchers, post-doctoral fellows, PhD students, students enrolled in postgraduates schools, external collaborators).

The University will design a free, open and multi-level training offer with the aim, by 2030, of bringing all members of the academic community to a level where they are able to use Artificial Intelligence tools in a reliable, responsible and jointly agreed manner.

AI and Data Protection

2

The use of Artificial Intelligence tools within the University must always comply with the principles, best practices and legal provisions governing the protection of personal data and the confidentiality of any information related to individuals (privacy). Notably, the principle of data minimisation requires users to exercise special caution when entering information into AI tools, and to only enter the information necessary to achieve the intended purpose.

AI tools not already authorised or "certified" by the University and the offices dealing with technology recognition, procurement and administration of IT systems are subject to thorough evaluation (by the Ethics Committee, by ad-hoc commissions, or in accordance with the provisions of specific regulations) before they can be cleared for use.

3. AI, Transparency and Traceability

The use of Artificial Intelligence tools to perform one's activities (carrying out administrative tasks, doing research, studying, writing papers or the final thesis) must be **clearly stated** and **transparent**.

In particular, users must specify, inter alia: i) the database queried; ii) the search queries and keywords entered;

iii) the actual tool(s) used. Furthermore, users must ensure the **traceability** of all operations performed by Artificial Intelligence systems, as required by EU legislation.

4. AI, Data Quality and Inclusiveness

The output of Artificial Intelligence tools must be carefully examined in order to prevent or mitigate the risk of **biased results** linked to specific characteristics of an individual or a group, with particular regard to vulnerable groups. To this end, it is paramount to ensure the **quality** of all data used by the

system (input data, training data, validation data). Likewise, access to automated systems should be based on the principle of technological **neutrality**, without barriers or restrictions.

5. AI and Environmental Sustainability

Artificial Intelligence tools can perform multiple useful functions, but are also **energy-intensive**. Before deciding to adopt or use an Artificial Intelligence tool, users should

assess its environmental impact, and limit its use to instances where the tool in question is truly necessary for their work, study or research activity.

6. AI and Cybersecurity

Like any IT invention, Artificial Intelligence systems are exposed to **cyberattacks**. Therefore, users must always pay **heightened attention** to the protection

of their devices, to the veracity of databases, to the risk of data poisoning, and to the reliability of AI system manufacturers and distributors.

7. AI, Accountability and Human Oversight

The University undertakes to comply with all legal obligations, particularly those related to data protection, cybersecurity, copyright, infrastructure safety, plagiarism, and the EU legal framework on Artificial Intelligence.

Everybody must work together to ensure that Artificial Intelligence is not used in violation of these principles

and the applicable rules of professional ethics. As required by the laws in force, all Artificial Intelligence systems used within the University must be subject to human oversight capable of intervening to disable/block the Artificial Intelligence system and to correct, reinterpret or even overturn its output.

It is the responsibility of each user to assess and decide whether it is advisable to resort to Artificial Intelligence tools for a certain task. Each user must commit to **using AI tools and AI output consciously and carefully**.

8. AI and Responsibility

The University provides users with detailed operating guidelines, as well as assistance and support, to ensure that Artificial Intelligence systems are always used with due caution.

9. AI and Governance

The University promotes data-driven processes, provided that they are ethically and legally compliant. Therefore, users are not allowed to enter "sensitive" personal data and data that could potentially harm the University (confidential minutes, confidential information, information with significant economic value, information linked

to the protection of the University's intellectual and industrial property) into Artificial Intelligence systems, unless this is absolutely necessary for them to complete their tasks. Should this be the case, the University will conduct preliminary evaluations before authorising the process in question.

Respecting laws, best practices, and internationally-shared ethical principles is a top priority for the University of Milan.

10. AI and Lawfulness

The whole academic community must adhere to the principles described in this document.

AI ETHICS

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